

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

New interfacial agent for enhanced interfacial shear strength in PPS/Carbon composites

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Objectives of the thesis

1) UNDERSTANDING AND CHARACTERIZATION OF THE CARBON-PPS INTERPHASE

Interphase : 3D area where the composition and the properties of the matrix and the fiber differs from their bulk properties.

Importance of the interphase in composites:

- Stress Transfer
- Ageing resistance

Interphase resistance depends on:

Thermodynamic adhesion – Chemical adhesion – Mechanical adhesion - Environnement

2) OPTIMIZATION OF THE COMPOSITE'S MECHANICAL PROPERTIES VIA INTERPHASE MODIFICATION

Effect of carbon fiber surface chemistry

Influence of the compatibilizing agent on the polymer matrix

SUMMARY

Fiber surface analysis

Matrix compatibilization

Adhesion measurements

- Carbon fibers
- Polyphenylene Sulfide

- Measurement systems
- Results

Carbon fiber surfaces – scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

CFs – Sized Carbon fiber

CFns – Non sized Carbon fiber

CFnt – Non treated Carbon fiber

Sizing is not applied homogeneously
Roughness is the same between CFs & CFns but seems different from CFnt
→ Sizing analysis is required

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Chemical analysis of the sizing

FTIR measurements (ATR)

¹H NMR spectra

Soxhlet extraction

Mass
20g

Conditions
THF
T=66°C
t=24h

Sizing
content =
1,5wt%

CFs
Sizing

Analysis indicates a Dgeba sizing
Best Correlation with Epikote 255™ (Hexion)
→ DGEBA + water emulsifier (water size bath ?)

NMR analysis confirms the presence of DGEBA
Additional peaks are found
→ Reflect the presence of other molecules

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Surface energy measurement (single fiber contact angle measurement – OWRK)

Surface analysis (XPS)

Reference	C	O	N	Si	Autres (<0.5%at.)
CFs	76.5	21.6	1.5	-	S, Cl, Sn
CFns	84.5	9.5	5.5	-	Sn
CFnt	93.9	3.3	2.4	0.5	-

Reference	C-C / C-H	C-O / C-N	C=O / O-C-O	O-C=O
CFs	59	37	3	1
CFns	94	1	5	-
CFnt	96	1	-	3

Sizing Oxidation

The presence of the sizing decreases the total surface energy
The classement of fibers by polarity is : CFns > CFs > CFnt
CFs has the highest oxygen content due to the presence of DGEBA

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Polyphenylene sulfide

Fortron 0320 from Celanese

Linear semi-crystalline polymer
 $T_g = 90^\circ\text{C}$
 $T_m = 280^\circ\text{C}$
 $M_w = 56,000 \text{ g/mol}$

Interests

Chemical resistance
 Mechanical properties
 Heat resistance
 Low flammability

PPS/ImCl blend

IDEA : Use of compatibilizing agent based on imidazolium salt

- **Reactive groups**
- **Withstand thermal process**
- **Pi stacking with PPS**

Extrusion process

T=310°C
Speed = 100rpm
Time = 2 min
Nitrogen atmosphere

Reference	Processing	% PPS	% ImCl
G0320-G	Y	100	0
G0320_ImCl	Y	95	5

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Thermal stability

ATR - Infrared spectroscopy

Presence of ImCl is verified ≈ 3 wt%
ImCl signal is found inside G0320-ImCl IR absorbance

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Thermal properties - crystallization analysis

G0320-G

300°C – 340°C : suppression of pre-existing nuclei

340°C – 380°C : thermal history removed

G0320-ImCl

Low influence of holding temperature on Tc

Materials characterisation

- Carbon fibers
- **Polyphenylene Sulfide**

Adherence Measurement

- Measurement systems
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Conclusion

Thermal properties - crystallization analysis

Extrusion process enhances crystallization
→ chain alignment & impurities

Nucleating effect of the ImCl

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Crystalline morphology - transmission electron microscopy

The crystalline microstructure of PPS is formed by Spherulites

ImCl forms aggregate into the matrix with low adherence with PPS : snatching under the oscillating blade

Modification of the microstructure occurs with ImCl

→ Smaller crystalline domain [Lins] [Yang]

Confirm the nucleating effect of ImCl

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- **Measurement systems**
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Micromechanical tests

- Pull-out
- Microbond
- Push-out
- Fragmentation
- Broutman test

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Pull-out test

Microbond test

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The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) is given by :

$$\tau = \frac{F_{max}}{2\pi r_f l_e}$$

Other models exist in the literature but this one is :

- Simple
- Comparative
- Well employed

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Pull-out test

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Microbond test

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PPS/Carbon fiber

- According to microbond and pull-out tests : adherence between **CFs / PPS** and **CFns / PPS** are in the **same range**
- The adherence between **CFnt / PPS** is lower : this fiber has the lowest surface energy and polar component – and its roughness seems limited.

PPS compatibilized /Carbon fiber

- Microbond and pull-out measurements confirm the increase of IFSS for **CFs/PPS_ImCl**, **CFns/PPS_ImCl** and **CFnt/PPS_ImCl**.
- This result seems to be linked to the enhancement of the crystallization because few reactive functions are provided by **CFnt**
- However chemical reactions between **CFs** and **CFns** surface can occur with ImCl but it should be limited because of the distribution of ImCl in the matrix

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ImCl influence

Improved Crystallization Transformation

→ High cooling rate supported

High Interfacial shear Strength

→ IFSS increased by 25%

→ Should lead to high mechanical properties on composites

Perspectives

Influence of other nucleating agents on IFSS measurements

ImCl sizing on carbon fibers